

A Pilot Study of a Custom GPT for the 2024 RCOphth Curriculum

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Abstract

Background

Large language models are increasingly used in medical education, with evidence suggesting they enhance learning by synthesising information, supporting personalised education, and improving accessibility (1). The 2024 Royal College of Ophthalmologists (RCOphth) curriculum introduced significant structural changes. These included defined training levels and a revised assessment framework. In response, we developed a CustomGPT tool designed to support curriculum-related queries. We then evaluated its usability and effectiveness for both trainees and consultants.

Methods

A CustomGPT was developed on OpenAI's platform using GPT-4o, trained exclusively on the official 2024 RCOphth OST curriculum documents. The model was restricted to the source material uploaded directly in PDF format. External web access was disabled to ensure accuracy and reduce the potential for misleading information. A system prompt was used to ensure the model's responses remained directly aligned with the uploaded curriculum documents, further limiting the risk of generating inaccurate or external information. A pilot validation study was conducted to assess whether the CustomGPT provided relevant answers and was easy to use. The tool was distributed to ophthalmology trainees (ST1–ST7) and consultant trainers. Quantitative feedback data was collected using a structured survey that assessed accuracy, usability, and likelihood of recommending the tool to others. Qualitative feedback was also collected with the aim of highlighting key strengths, areas for improvement, and suggestions for future development.

Results

A total of 28 respondents completed the initial survey, comprising 14 consultants and 14 trainees or fellows. Respondents were at a diverse range of training levels. Of these, 21% (6/28) reported themselves as regular users of AI tools. The GPT's

response relevance received a mean rating of 4.21 out of 5. Ease of use was rated highly, with a mean score of 4.38 out of 5, while overall satisfaction with the system achieved a mean score of 4.1 out of 5. Respondents rated the likelihood of recommending the tool to other trainees or supervisors with a mean score of 7.9 out of 10. A total of 21 out of 28 participants gave a score of 8 or higher. This indicates that a large majority were very satisfied with this approach to answering curriculum queries.

Qualitative feedback highlighted that the tool was easy to use, quick to navigate, and provided helpful links to relevant curriculum content. Limitations included occasional technical issues and difficulties handling some specific or complex queries. Suggested improvements included integration with the RCOphth website and enhanced linking to the trainee e-portfolio.

Conclusion

To our knowledge, this is the first pilot study exploring the use of a custom large language model specifically trained on any medical curriculum. The CustomGPT demonstrated strong usability and relevance in helping users navigate the 2024 RCOphth curriculum, with high satisfaction among both trainees and consultants. The next stage of the study will involve validation of responses against those of the curriculum lead, followed by potential integration into the RCOphth website. These findings highlight a promising real-world application of large language models in medical education - saving time and improving access to information.

Keywords: CustomGPT, Large Language model, Medical Education

References

1. Lucas HC, Upperman JS, Robinson JR. A systematic review of large language models and their implications in medical education. *Med Educ.* 2024;58(11):1276-85.